

An indica source of male sterile cytoplasm and its fertility restoration for hybrid rice breeding

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The search for alternate sources of sterile cytoplasm in hybrid rice breeding is a priority because more than 90% of the rice hybrids released throughout the world are based on a single sterile cytoplasm—wild abortive (WA). Because of the very narrow genetic base provided by the single cytoplasmic source, hybrids carrying this cytoplasm can become vulnerable to pests and diseases found associated with it.

We observed reciprocal differences for pollen sterility in the F_2 generation in a number of crosses. In one such cross (Pusa 743/Pusa 33), male sterile segregants were observed during 1992, whereas in another reciprocal (Pusa 33/Pusa 743) all the F_2 plants were fertile. This indicated that Pusa 743 has sterility-inducing cytoplasm. Of several breeding lines tested for fertility restoration in this cytoplasm, 30% were found to be restorers. Initially, 21% of the lines were identified as maintainers. But only 10% showed a stable reaction for sterility maintenance in the later backcross generations. This indicated that fertility restoration was governed by a single dominant gene, although a majority of the crosses showed significant deviations from Mendelian segregation because of a deficit of recessives. Japonica rices are likely to maintain sterility in this cytoplasm. Three cytoplasmic male sterile lines with a stable sterility reaction were developed. Pusa 1127A was found to be agronomically promising. ■

Male sterile lines for hybrid rice breeding

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Experience with hybrid maize indicates the utility of diverse cytoplasmic sources as a source of cytoplasmic male sterility. Crop heterogeneity is desirable for the sustainability of commercial hybrids. We studied the morphological and physiological characters of male sterile lines belonging to diverse cytoplasm. We studied eight male sterile lines belonging to wild abortive types (V20 A, Zhengshan 97 A, BO A, Jin 23 A, and Zhi A), IDR or Indonesian paddy rice type (U1 A), dwarf abortive type (Xieqinzao A), and BT or japonica type (80-4 A) during the winter season of 1993-94 in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line was planted in a single row, with a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. The crop was maintained as per recommended practices.

From a nursery 10-, 20-, and 30-d-old seedling samples were taken for study. Clean plant samples were collected from the nursery using a digging plate and the roots were freed of soil by washing them with water. From five seedlings per replication, observations were recorded on length, volume by water displacement in a burette, and weight of root and shoot portions. Total tillers, panicle-bearing tillers, and plant height at the vegetative (60 d) and flowering stages were also recorded for each test line. Pollen reaction was studied using an I-KI (1%) solution. The percentage of a certain type of pollen was calculated by the ratio of its occurrence to the total number of pollen grains in a microscopic field. Seed set on male sterile

lines was studied in isolation by bagging.

Some lines that expressed good seedling growth and vigor in the nursery were Zhi A (root length, shoot volume, and shoot weight at 30 d), Xieqinzao A (root and shoot length at 30 d, root and shoot volume at 30 d), and Jin 23 A (shoot length at three stages of sampling and shoot weight at 20 and 30 d).

Jin 23 A, Zhi A, and 80-4A were tall at the vegetative and flowering stages. The lines flowered in 85-95 d, with Jin 23 A being early and Zhengshan 97 A late to flower. The exertion of stigmas outside the floret was well expressed in BO A, Jin 23 A, U1 A, and Zhi A. Lines Jin 23 A, V20 A, and Zhengshan 97 A showed 100% unstained and irregular-shaped pollen, whereas Zhi A, BO A, and U1 A showed 99-99.5% sterile irregular pollen. Xieqinzao A had 5% stained pollen and 80-4 A had all pollen grains circular, of which 50% were stained. Line BO A had a maximum panicle-bearing tillers and was on a par with Jin 23 A, Zhi A, V 20 A, and Xieqinzao A. There was no seed set in the panicle bag. ■

Fertility-altering conditions of promising thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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Characterizing thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines with respect

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to fertility alteration and evaluating their utility in two-line heterosis breeding were the objectives of the present investigation.

TGMS lines SA2, F61, JP8-8-1s, JP1, IC10, ID24, and JP24A identified at DRR, Hyderabad, and IR32364, IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949, received from IRRI, Philippines, were screened. These TGMS lines were grown under constant and varying temperature and daylength combination regimes in a growth chamber. They were also grown in fields under staggered sowing and ratooning over seasons. Lines SA2, JP8-8-1s, F61, IC10, and ID24 were found to be interactive with photoperiod; therefore, they are designated as PTGMS. JP1 and the TGMS lines from IRRI were more or less independent of photoperiod influence. The critical fertility point, the temperature at which maximum fertility occurred, ranged from 20 to 26 °C in various PTGMS lines and from 20 to 30 °C for other TGMS lines. The critical sterility point, the temperature at which total sterility occurred, was at 25 °C and above for PTGMS lines and at 32 °C for TGMS lines. Reverse TGMS line JP24A showed total sterility below 26 °C and complete fertility at 28 °C and above.

The temperature at which physiological sterility occurred (biological lower limit) and the temperature at which sensitivity for various lines was identified differed. PTGMS lines were stable for sterility under field conditions (March-June), whereas TGMS lines reverted back to fertility under cloudy weather and cooler night temperatures. Stable sterility in PTGMS lines may be because of the dual role of temperature and photoperiod or their interaction. Spikelet fertility under field conditions ranged from 7 to 21% and 11-70% seed set was recorded in a growth chamber for PTGMS lines. This warrants a search to identify critical areas for their seed multiplication. ■

Identifying rice genotypes with the TGMS trait suitable for north India

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The discovery of the environment-sensitive genic male sterility (EGMS) system laid the foundation for replacing the three-line system with the simpler and more efficient two-line system for hybrid rice seed production. EGMS includes photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) and thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) systems. The required day-length differences do not occur in our rice seasons for PGMS seed production. Therefore, we attempted to develop suitable TGMS lines in India.

We studied fertility responses to temperature in 15 TGMS lines during 1995-96 under natural environmental conditions at Pantnagar, situated at 29° N latitude, 79.3° E longitude, and 244 m above sea level. The aim was to identify suitable TGMS lines for the northwestern regions of Uttar Pradesh. The TGMS lines were sown on various planting dates and maintained in the nethouse or glasshouse.

Five TGMS lines showed seasonal fertility-sterility transformation under field conditions. These lines were characterized by sterility under high temperature (mean daily average >29 °C) and fertility transformation at low temperature (mean daily average 26-28 °C). IR68292-10-34-6, IR68292-10-34-25, and IR68949-5-31-34 were completely sterile when sown in February to April but partially fertile when planted after the second fortnight of May. IR68945-33-4-14-4 and IR68945-33-4-14-7 showed complete sterility when sown in February to May and were partially fertile when sown in June and July. IR68292-10-34-6, IR68292-10-34-25, and IR68949-5-31-34 may be exploited for hybrid seed production with off-season sowing in February to April. Seeds of these lines can be multiplied by sowing in July to August, whereas TGMS lines IR68945-33-4-14-4 and IR68945-33-4-14-7 can be used to produce hybrid seed in the main season, and parental lines can be multiplied by sowing in July and August. To exploit these lines in developing commercial hybrids, further studies are in progress to test their stability at several locations in the region and also under controlled temperature conditions. ■

Genetics

Zhenong 921: a new indica rice variety with high yield and blast resistance

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Zhenong 921, a new semidwarf indica rice variety, is derived from Zhongzhe 1/K 125-34 and is suitable for the double-cropped area of southern China. It was registered by Zhejiang Province in 1997 as an early rice variety.

About 2,000 ha in southern China are planted to Zhenong 921, which has a growth duration of about 109 d. Zhenong 921 has a high, stable yield potential under normal fertilization. It yielded 6.7-7.5 t ha⁻¹ in yield trials and its highest yield of 8.1 t ha⁻¹ was 9.3% more than that of the check in 1994. Its leaf blast and neck blast resistance scores were 1.6 and 1.9, compared with check Zhe 852, which scored 4.6 and 3.4, respectively. Zhenong 921 has cold resistance in the seedling stage and good lodging resistance.

Tables 1 and 2 show morpho-agronomic characters. Zhenong 921 is awnless and medium-grained. The milled rice length and the ratio of length to width are 6.5 mm and 2.5,